

“Musical tastes and subjective experience of psychophysiological tensions”

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Introduction

This article reports the results of a research carried out for my master degree thesis in psychology, in 1999, concerning the relations between musical genres preferences and subjective body experience, with the aim of contributing to a better understanding of correlations between aesthetic musical experience and processes of construction of the Personality. The research is subdivided in two parts: the first part consists of the analysis of the literature relating to musical tastes; the second consists of the analysis of the results of a survey on relations between musical genres preferences and self-perception of muscle tensions, carried out on a sample of students of the University of Rome “La Sapienza”. The work thus proposes a psychophysiological interpretation of individual musical preferences, in order to integrate the findings of the studies in the psycho-sociological field on this issue with the analysis of individual body experiences, according to the Psychophysiological Model of Ruggieri (1987, 1988, 1997). On the basis of the assumptions of this theoretical approach, a hypothesis was formulated about the relation between musical genres preferences and self-perceived postural tensions, the body’s equivalent of the concept of the Integration of the Self (Kohut 1976). Furthermore, an attempt was made to analyse the structure of musical tastes and of self-perceived muscle tensions, with the aim of identifying possible stable patterns of the latent factors that could be used as models in future researches of this kind.

The thesis work starts with an overview of the most important studies concerning the musical preferences, classified by discipline: personality psychology, social psychology and sociology; they all put a focus on the characteristics of the personality and on the social aspects associated to the

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musical preferences. The second part of the thesis is dedicated to the description of the assumptions of this research, i.e. to the contributions made by different disciplines to the elaboration of the research hypothesis: from body-oriented psychology; to physiological and neurophysiological studies of musical listening; to psycho physiological approaches focused on the self-perception of muscle tensions in response to the music; to the psychophysiological model of Ruggieri focused on the analysis of narcissism and of the aesthetic experience associated to the music (Ruggieri, 1997). The last part of the research work analyses the results of the survey conducted to explore the correlations between musical preferences and self-perception of the muscle tensions.

1. The studies on music preferences in the Personality Psychology

In the Personality Psychology field, attempts have been made to establish a correlation between specific music genres preferences and stable personality traits, developing a specific methodology for assessing music preferences and for comparing them with the scores of personality tests.

The studies on music preferences in this field generally refer to four main theoretical approaches:

- a) Cattell's Trait Theory of Personality
- b) Eysenck Theory of Personality
- c) Zuckerman Sensation Seeking Model
- d) "Big Five" Model

The first researches in this field are based on measurement of preferences for short music excerpts submitted to the subjects (Cattell & Saunders, 1954; Keston & Pinto, 1955). In other cases, the subjects were asked to list the preferred composers (Payne, 1967). In the 80's, the music preference started to be measured by a Likert-type scale, with reference to a list of music genres, which included the names of the most representative authors. Cattell was the first to hypothesize that there was a stable correlation between musical tastes

and personality traits (Cattell & Kline, 1982), seeking to identify the traits responsible for different musical genres, with the aim of defining the types of music that could prove to be “therapeutic” for specific personality types. For this purpose, he created an appropriate measurement tools, the Music Preference Test Personality IPAT (Cattell & Eber 1954).

Payne (1967) proposed a reinterpretation of Cattell’s researches on the grounds of the Eysenck Theory of Personality (1960), identifying a relation between stable/neurotic temperament and classical/romantic musical tastes. He proposed as well another method for preference assessment, which requested from the subjects to indicate a series of preferred composers and the their most representative pieces. The researches carried out by Daoussis and Mckelvie (1986), who compared the music preferences with extroversion/introversion, remain described within the Eysenck Theory of Personality (Eysenck, 1967, 1970). The same is the case of Keston and Pinto (1955), who examined the relations between the preferences and “intellectual introversion, as well of Chapman and Williamson (1976), Roe (1985) and Rawlings, Hodge, Sherr and Dempsey (1995), who studied relations between music preferences and the “psychoticism” scores. In particular, the latter authors assessed musical preferences both through direct listening of representative pieces of four different types of music (dance, easy listening, classical music and hard rock/heavy metal), as well through the Little & Zuckerman Musical Preference Scale (1985). The mentioned scale constitutes an important contribution to this field of study. With this instrument, Zuckerman aims to overcome the limits of the previous studies – based mainly on the listening of the musical pieces selected by the researchers – by submitting to the subjects a wide list of different types of music of which they were asked to indicate the level of preference. The scale has been created to bring to light the relations between the musical preferences and the construct “sensation seeking” by Zuckerman (1979). In reference to this, Arnett (1992) has outlined the role of sensation seeking as a mediating variable on the relationship between the preferences for hard rock and heavy metal music and reckless behaviour.

More recent researches make reference to the 5 factors personality model and to the NEO-PI model. The research that analysed musical preferences by applying Big Five model was that of Dollinger (1993), where the scores of Little e Zuckerman Musical Preference Scale (1986) were compared to those measured by the NEO-PI Scale (Costa & McCrae, 1992).

2. Social aspects of music preferences

The role of social factors in music preferences has been highlighted by different disciplinary studies.

In particular, the sociology studies have paid special attention to the analysis of demographic indicators, identifying the relationship with socioeconomic status, gender and age (Schuessler, 1948). Other researchers have studied the role of the peer group in music preferences of adolescents (Johnstone & Katz, 1957). Boumann (1960) investigated the role of age, using an inventory of music preferences composed of the recordings of 50 musical works of "popular", classical and folk music; what he identified was a general preference for the pop music by the subjects of all ages and a tendency to prefer the classical music along with the age growth, as confirmed subsequently by Hallier and Leeper (1984). Christenson e Peterson (1988) have put a focus on gender differences in musical taste and outlined the centrality of two musical subcultures within adolescent culture - male and female subcultures - related to different patterns of music preferences. The studies of Wober (1984) e Warner (1984) have as well explored gender differences in music preferences.

Within the field of social psychology, the spotlight is put on the social and contextual nature of music preferences (Farnsworth 1950, 1969; Konecni 1979). A high number of studies are dedicated to the cultures and forms of the youth's distress. In particular, several of these studies examined the correlation of the preference for heavy metal music to antisocial behaviour (Wass et al., 1991; Took & Weiss, 1994), to drug abuse (in particular, of hard drugs such as heroin and cocaine) and to alcohol abuse (King 1988). In this

regard, Hansen and Hansen (1991) integrate a socio-cognitive analysis of the role of the music in the process of socialization of adolescents with the examination of their personality traits, drawing suggestions from the literature on the influences of the mass-media in the socialization of adolescents (Baxter, De Riemer, Landin, 1985; Ellis, 1983). More recently, special attention was paid to new synthetic drugs, in relation to the techno music and to the "rave party" phenomenon (Canevacci 1996; Lapassade 1998; Pochettino 1996; Pacoda 1996; Stefani 1996; Salvatore 1998).

The studies of cognitive psychology concerning the music preferences principally make reference to the analysis of characteristics of musical compositions, in relation to perceived "familiarity" and "complexity" as predictive parameters for music preferences (Burke & Gridley, 1990, Mull, 1957). Gaver and Mandler (1987) describe the representation of the structure of the music by the concept of "schema" (Mandler, 1984). In particular, remaining within the cognitive approach, Zenatti (1976) puts the focus on the spontaneous expression of musical taste, while Sloboda (1988) draws attention to the assessment of conformity to cultural rules.

3. Contributions to the elaboration of the hypothesis of the research

Different spheres of neurophysiological sciences, cognitive and body-based approaches have contributed to the definition of the present research. The main theoretical reference framework is constituted by the integrated psycho-physiological model by Ruggieri (1987). This model follows on from the interpretation of the kohutian theory of "narcissism" (Kohut, 1976) from a psycho-corporal perspective, which highlights the importance of the mind-body cohesion experience in the process of the construction of the Self. The "narcissism" thus becomes a complex process of integration of different functional levels of all physiological and psychological activities, characterized by a higher level of integration, such is the case of instinctive and emotional behaviour. The muscle activity produces also an "imitative decodification" of the stimulus, as a reproduction, in terms of muscular tensions, of the

characteristics of the "stimulus-figure", involved in the experience of pleasure (Ruggieri, 1997). The listening of different music genres, with different "stimulus-figure" relations, would be able to generate different experiences of pleasure-unpleasure in different subjects, depending on the basic tensions and on the capacity of managing different "reorganizations" of tensions, caused by the musical stimulus and linked to the emotional experiences aroused by the same. In this light, the musical preferences could be interpreted as the "research" of different "modulations" of tensions in relation to the process of "narcissism".

Nevertheless, the structure of this research has also been drawn from other similar disciplinary fields. Within the framework of the cognitive psychology, there exist a representation of the music as a structure constituted by a consecution of the "tension-distension", in reference to the analysis of the cognitive processes involved in the listening of the music (Imberty 1986; Lerdhall & Jackendoff 1983). Repp (1993) stresses the role of the corporal aspects, in relation to the sonic structure. The psychoanalysis emphasizes the role of the rhythm in the organization of human experience (Spitz 1965, Rechartd 1987). The body-based psychological approaches highlight the role of the muscle tensions in the psychological processes (Reich 1973, 1975; Lowen 1978, 1983). The physiology and neurophysiology draw attention to the different effects produced by the listening of different music genres at the neurophysiological level (Harrer & Harrer 1987, McFarland, 1985; Zimmermann et al. 1988; Clynes 1982).

4. Research results

The research was based on the hypothesis that exists a relationship between music preferences and subjective tension experience. These two aspects have been measured, the first, through an adapted Italian version of the Musical Preference Scale by Little and Zuckerman (1986) and the latter, through the Postural Tensions Questionnaire by Ruggieri, submitted to a sample of two hundred students of the Faculty of Psychology of the University of Rome "La

Sapienza". The Musical Preference Scale implies the evaluation on a Likert-type scale of the musical preferences of a series of musical genres for which are provided examples of names of authors and bands. The Postural Tensions Questionnaire consists of a self-evaluation of the subjective experience of tension in different body areas, using a rating from 1 to 10.

The collected data have been processed by the software SPSS, through the use of the statistical method of analysis of the main components. The analysis outlined a factorial structure of six factors for the musical tastes (Jazz-Blues, Rock-Metal, Electronic-Dance, Ethnic, Classical-Electronic listening music, Pop-commercial) and a factorial structure of four factors for the subjective experience of postural tension (Head, Limbs, Thorax-Pelvis, Back of the Body). Potential relationship between these two series of factors have been analysed using the Method of Correlations by Pearson. For the scores values that showed of statistical significance of 0.05, two correlations have been identified, between the preferences for music genre corresponding to the factor Jazz-Blues and the perception of tension in the area of body corresponding to the factor Limbs and between the preferences for music genre corresponding to the factor Ethnic and the perception of tension in the area of body corresponding to the factor Thorax-Pelvis.

In order to clarify the obtained results, the correlations between the six musical factor and the single body areas have been measured. For the levels of significance equal to 0.05, following relationships between music preference and self-perceived tension have emerged:

- between the preference for the music genres related to the factor Jazz-Blues and the perception of tension in the arms, legs, gluteus, mandible, eyes and thorax
- between the preference for the genres related to the factor Rock-Metal and the tensions in the abdomen, pubis and thorax
- between the preference for the genres related to the factor Ethnic and the tensions in the pubis and the abdomen

- between the preference for the genres related to the factor Classical – Electronic Listening Music and the tensions in the arms, lumbar region, shoulders and thorax

The mentioned results gain special significance if read in the light of the findings highlighted by the literature of psycho-corporeal imprint, regarding the relationships between music preferences, specific body areas and aggressiveness and sexuality (Lowen 1978, 1983; Reich 1973, 1975; Ruggieri 1987, 1988), which can provide starting points for further investigations. What emerges from this perspective are the correlations between the preference for the Jazz-Blues music and the parts of the body associated to the aggressiveness (arms, legs and mandible); between the preference for the Rock-Metal music and the parts of the body associated to the sexuality (abdomen and pubis) and between the preference for the Classical-Electronic Listening music and the parts of the body associated to the repression of aggressiveness (back of the body). In consideration of these findings, potential interactions arise between the aesthetic (musical) experience and subjective body sensations, the impulsive forces that are at the basis of the Psychoanalytic Theory (Freud 1933) and their interpretation in light of psychophysiological approach. In order to improve the understanding of these first findings, further investigations are necessary to integrate these distinct but complementary perspectives of analysis of the human experience.

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